

Exploring Place: A Pedagogical Journey in Spatial Planning Using the Place Standard Tool

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This paper presents the pedagogical outcomes of integrating the Place Standard Tool – an open-access survey tool for assessing places – into the learning experience of first-year spatial planning students to approach the concept of place and its connection to their discipline. The study, conducted within a case study in Rozenburg-Rotterdam, the Netherlands, focusses on examining the relationship between spatial dynamics and residents' interactions with their surroundings. Through field trips and a street survey, the students utilized collective mapping and the Place Standard Tool to assess people's perceptions of Rozenburg as a place, examining its challenges, pressures, and opportunities. The paper critically reflects on the methodological and pedagogical aspects of this integration, emphasizing the significance of the platial perspective in spatial planning education. Drawing from a hands-on pedagogical experience, the paper outlines the advantages of adopting the platial approach in the learning process, while also highlighting the challenges of introducing complex and theoretically loaded concepts such as place.

Keywords: place; street survey; teaching; education; learning; interdisciplinary

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1 Introduction

Place encompasses a myriad of perspectives and concerns, intricately interweaving the physical, social, and environmental fabric that shapes communities and influences the interpretation of our surroundings (Mocnik, 2022). However, due to its elusive nature, place challenges pedagogical efforts within the classroom. As educators in spatial planning, our goal was to equip first-year spatial planning students with the necessary tools and understanding to navigate this complex landscape. To fulfill this purpose, we embarked on a transformative pedagogical journey guided by the notion of place, employing multidisciplinary teaching strategies. Our case study was Rozenburg, a former town now situated within the administration of Rotterdam, the Netherlands. With an estimated population of 12,335, Rozenburg now resides amidst Europe's largest port. By engaging with the residents of this distinctive setting, our objective was to enable students to unveil diverse insights and considerations held by the community. This experience broadened our students' outlook and enhanced their understanding of the intricate relationships between individuals and their circumstances, which underlies spatial planning as discipline and practice.

The premise that initiated our pedagogical journey is rooted in Rozenburg's urban and environmental pressures, which affect the everyday life of residents and their relations to their surroundings. The notion of sense of place is then invoked to capture and encompass such relations, both on a practical level of meeting residents' needs by their locale, as well as on the level of deeper personal connections,

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perceptions, sense of identity and belonging, among others. The initial assumption suggested that sense of place of residents might be influenced by urban and environmental pressures undergone by a particular locale. The students set out to test it and unveil the possible ways of such influence on residents' perception of their place. Drawing upon the multidisciplinary discourse surrounding the concept of place, we emphasized the significance of such a platial approach for comprehending spatial dynamics from a planning perspective. By shedding light on the interplay between spatial factors and the interactions of individuals with their surroundings, this exploration offered valuable insights into the multifaceted relationship among place, its inhabitants, and the field of spatial planning.

2 Framework

The pedagogical setting of this experience is anchored in a two-semester study project within the Spatial Planning bachelor programme at TU Dortmund University¹. The module provides hands-on training in research skills for first-year spatial planning students and fosters a practical understanding of applying knowledge in future practice. This co-supervised self-learning project approached Rozenburg's dynamics, including expanding industries, population factors, and economic activities driving the demand for land. It also addressed pressing issues such as air pollution from port logistics and nearby industrial clusters as well as the impact of the climate crisis and rising water levels.

One of the challenges associated with the pedagogical format was to strike a balance between providing a robust framework to support students and leaving enough room for their independent and creative contributions. The conceptual richness of place, complemented by the suggested methodological framework, facilitated this balance. Students had the flexibility to work within the module framework and to develop their own problem statement. For this matter, they delved into specific pressures encountered in Rozenburg, such as land-intensive industries and ongoing construction projects like the highway tunnel (*Blankenburgverbinding* in Dutch), as well as upgrading mitigation initiatives of the *Green Belt* around Rozenburg. The research question that guided their undertakings forward was formulated as: 'How could urban and environmental pressures be affecting the sense of place of the inhabitants of Rozenburg?'. This question directly reflects the struggles that the students underwent in understanding the inability to have definitive and full-rounded answers regarding place and its perception. In fact, a central goal of our pedagogical process was not only to introduce students to an instrumental approach to place in planning but also to expand their outlook toward a broader discussion on the nature of space in spatial disciplines. Students were encouraged to reflect on a variety of terms employed in spatial and geographical disciplines to refer to what Thrift (2003) called 'the fundamental stuff of geography'. As the author points out, 'space is not just a commonsense external background to human and social action'. Therefore, if we are to take the learning process in spatial disciplines to its roots, we might need to start by reflecting on fundamental concepts, which are accepted to be understood and established to such a degree that obscures them from deep and critical understanding. Thus, the students were encouraged to craft their own stance in the space and place debate, having in mind not only deeper conceptual understanding but also navigating and developing an approach to place tailored to the project's goals and their study in Rozenburg.

Delving into the above-mentioned topics, the students anchored their understanding of place in a human geographical perspective, acknowledging the multidisciplinary reach of the notion of place in social sciences, humanities, psychology, environmental studies, inter alia (Buttimer and Seamon, 2015; Relph, 1976; Tuan, 1977). To better comprehend the concept, the students approached place through the lens of sense of place as a multidimensional concept, comprised of four dimensions – the self, environment, social interaction, and time (Beidler and Morrison, 2016). Unpacking each, they foregrounded the dimension of the self as pivotal for transforming space into place, asserting the central role of the human subjective side to it. Moving further, the tripartite construct of sense of place as consisting of place identity, place attachment, and place dependence (Jorgensen and Stedman, 2001) has been added to the study framework. To reconcile the heterogeneous conceptualizations of dimensions while retaining coherent conceptual support for the study, the students undertook the above tripartite scheme, wherein place attachment is located at the core, and influenced by place identity and place dependence. The main challenge faced by them in such harmonization was to find how these three constructs correspond with social, physical, and environmental aspects of place. It became clear that these constructs are intricately intertwined and could not be disentangled into

simplistic attributions. Proof of the last is reflected in the physical facilities that were solely associated with place dependence. Throughout this process, the students developed an understanding that an individual's experience of place is a holistic phenomenon. It encompasses elements such as the physical and built environment, social interactions, and cultural experiences as well as personal experiences, emotions, and behaviours towards a place, which all together result in a bond between an individual and a place (Nelson et al., 2020).

While adopting such an approach, the students faced the challenge to translate the conceptual premises into operational categories to be applied to the study. For these endeavours, the Place Standard Tool² (PST) was proposed as a resource. This place-based tool was developed by a public-private alliance in Scotland known as the Place Standard partners³. This participatory assessment resource has been adapted for case studies in various contexts (Gjorgjev et al., 2022; Kleopa et al., 2019; Ocaña et al., 2022), and in our case, it helped to articulate the efforts to understand the fluidity of the concept of place and the inherent subjectivities of sense of place. The tool acted as a catalyst for understanding the perception of place held by Rozenburg's inhabitants across social, physical, and environmental dimensions. The PST provides a 14-dimensional graph framework that sheds light on areas for improvement based on the community's perspective. These dimensions are organized into five major categories: Movement, Space, Resources, Civic, and Stewardship. Movement focusses on safe and sustainable transportation, while Space examines design and usage to promote community engagement. Resources assess accessibility, aiming to reduce inequality. Civic emphasizes building quality and accessibility, and Stewardship involves care, influence, and democratic decision-making. The PST provides a community-friendly framework for assessing the quality and potential for improvement of neighbourhoods while addressing their inequalities, making it a suitable resource for spatial planning practices. The initial way to address the said challenge taken by the group was based on searching for potential links between three broad sub-notions of sense of place – place attachment, place identity, place dependence – and wider categories incorporated into the PST (i.e., Space, Resources, Civic, Stewardship, Movement). The students based their reasoning on such initial assumptions as, e.g., linking place dependence to the availability and wealth of resources provided by place, or attributing a stronger sense of place identity to a higher degree of stewardship towards place. However, such an approach soon revealed itself as rather simplistic and unfeasible to achieve, as it proved impossible to disentangle all interwoven aspects into clear-cut compartments which fit neatly into a general picture of a place, like compatible puzzle pieces. The place asserted itself as a way more complex and dynamic creature, where different facets are feeding into each other, overlapping and sometimes contradicting each other. This realization reinforced the understanding pointed out by Erfani (2022) that a single integrated conceptual framework for sense of place is implausible across all fields, highlighting the need to develop or adapt frameworks for each research case.

3 Methodology as a Journey

This project provided an opportunity for students to approximate the material and social fabric of the site, reflecting on the theoretical and conceptual foundations of planning. An exploratory field trip allowed the students to gain a first-hand impression of Rozenburg and test preliminary findings against the immediate experience on the ground. While filling field observation forms and recording their observations in respective assigned sectors of Rozenburg, the students were asked to adopt a place perspective from their own position as newcomers getting familiar with the site, as familiarity with surroundings builds the first bridge to conceive an area as a distinct and specific place. Synthesizing the gathered observations in a collective mapping exercise, the students had to pin down their heterogeneous impressions to the abstract 2-dimensional surface of the Rozenburg plan, reflecting in the process how location-sensitive some things are and how all-pervasive some others. Based on this first field trip experience and interim conclusions, the students had to face their preconceptions and assumptions, reconsidering the pressures and dynamics in Rozenburg. The fieldwork revealed a different view of the community, challenging the notion of vivid and omnipresent pressures while highlighting the positive aspects of Rozenburg. Despite being affected by some external pressures, Rozenburg's residents seem to enjoy abundant greenery and easy access to water bodies. Therefore, the research evolved and the efforts shifted towards methodological and operational considerations, particularly regarding the adaptation and application of the PST during the second field trip. As reported above, throughout

the learning process the students more and more recognized the complexity of the sense of place phenomenon and the difficulty of categorizing it in a straightforward manner. However, they found that the thematic content of the PST provided a suitable framework for exploring everyday life concerns in Rozenburg. It allowed them to structure conversations and engage with the local community while registering these interactions in a structured fashion, gathering insights that shed light on place attachment, place identity, and place dependence, albeit not in plain fashion. The PST categories did not streamline directly into the three constructs, however, the students were able to elucidate some links across them. For example, resources of place feed not only into place dependence but constitute a part of place identity and attachment as well. Apart from conceptual and methodological considerations, the students worked through practical matters of applying the PST. Before its on-site and online application, the PST underwent a testing process within the university context, leading to further adjustments. One of the challenges faced was transforming the PST into survey sheets that were convenient and intuitive for quick on-the-spot completion. Additionally, a major ordeal arose from the language barrier encountered by German-speaking students in an English-speaking research group working within a Dutch-speaking community. The language barrier was one of the aspects that underscored the significance of being receptive to the local context in a place-based setting and stimulated the students to reflect on the role of cultural differences in general while engaging with places from diverse backgrounds. The PST itself is intended and designed to be applicable across a variety of contexts and locations since it is structured around very general basic categories. In this regard, it is telling that the Dutch adaptation of the PST⁴ did not introduce major changes but offered a Dutch translation of the basic framework. However, it is at the level of content and application of the PST where cultural differences are set to play a crucial role. Each conversation held around the PST themes carries unique outlooks, perspectives, and subjective inputs from both residents and researchers. Therefore, careful calibration and great sensitivity are needed in the very process of dialogue, and subsequent interpretation of obtained results. The issue of cultural differences becomes even more pertinent for the comparability of the PST results across different localities and countries. The unified PST graph plotting the numerical scores for categories might compel us to draw conclusions from mere juxtaposition of graphs, which might be erroneous if a larger cultural context is not accounted for.

To ensure comprehensive coverage when applying the PST in their second fieldwork, the students committed to three consecutive days at the central square of Rozenburg, with shifts from 8 am to 9 pm. In addition, individual surveys were randomly distributed in diverse neighbourhoods, inviting residents to take part in the online version of the PST survey. The on-site participant selection followed a random sampling approach, avoiding bias towards specific individuals. This methodology resulted in a statistically significant sample, with well-distributed age groups and genders given the format of the street survey, indicating a low risk of bias. The students successfully collected 343 on-site and 25 online responses, accounting for approximately 2.98% of Rozenburg's population actively involved in the surveying process. Among the participants, 49% identified as female, 50% as male, and 1% as diverse. The surveyed age groups were as follows: 2% aged 0–15, 18% aged 15–25, 29% aged 26–45, 26% aged 46–65, and 23% aged 65+, aligning with the neighbourhood's demographic profile except for the youngest age group of 0–15 due to the lack of autonomy for children to take part in such activities.

Despite the noticeable construction noises and occasional chemical smells resulting from the neighbourhood's proximity to industrial complexes, the resulting graph (Figure 1) averaging all of the responses exhibits an overall positive sense of place in Rozenburg. The main concerns expressed by the surveyed residents focussed on 'Public Transport' (Movement), 'Housing and Community' (Civic), and 'Influence and Control' (Stewardship). However, it is important to acknowledge that the survey results also revealed positive elements. Respondents expressed satisfaction with 'Traffic and Parking' (Movement), 'Natural Space' (Space), and 'Work and Economy' (Resources). As the project is currently in its final stages, further analysis will be conducted to examine specific areas and data behaviour.

4 Pedagogical Takeaways and Challenges

By incorporating the PST into our pedagogical journey, a comprehensive understanding of the multi-faceted aspects that shape places can be acquired. It helped us to guide a conceptual discussion and envision the scope of the notions of place without losing sight of the discipline that hosts this study project. It allowed students in an early stage of their careers to engage with the local community,

Figure 1: Place Standard Tool resulting graph for average responses in the surveying process in Rozenburg, the Netherlands (Created through <http://www.ourplace.scot/tool>)

unveil diverse perspectives, and consider the lived experiences and concerns of people. Consequently, the tool becomes a resource for students to evaluate, analyse, and monitor places, identify areas for improvement, and generate well-informed recommendations for spatial planning and development projects. Ultimately, the inclusion of the PST enhances the spatial planning process by incorporating community input and fostering a more inclusive and people-centred approach.

The concept of place offers a potent outlet that harmonizes various spatial considerations with human perspectives. It grounds the dynamics of different scales into distinct and tangible locales while imbuing them with social relations and collective meanings. Within an academic structure, an open and guided research project provides a significant opportunity for students to approach a specific case study as both academic researchers and future planning practitioners. This approach encourages reflection on the theoretical and conceptual foundations of planning while developing practical methods and hands-on approaches in the field. At the same time, the fruitful nature of the platial approach can pose challenges in achieving learning outcomes at the entry level of spatial planning. The concept of place, being open to a nearly infinite number of interpretations and approaches, exceeds the basic premises needed for an empirical case study, thereby charging it with theoretical depth. The latter demands a higher level of comprehension from students, which needs to be developed and nurtured along the way.

5 Conclusions

The journey is yet to be accomplished, as the students are still working on finalizing the research at the time of writing. It can be confidently asserted, however, that the implementation of the platial approach in the module has proven to be a rewarding framework despite the challenges, both conceptual and pedagogical ones, brought by such a complex topic. The complexity and holistic nature of place eludes a straightforward operationalization via rigid and unresponsive methods, which demands thoughtful and careful engagement with it in the classroom settings, and even more so in the future planning practice of students. This approach has not only allowed the execution of a robust empirical case study but also

facilitated the attainment of valuable academic learning outcomes and high-level theoretical knowledge, which is crucial for spatial planning as an academic discipline. Additionally, it has demonstrated its added value by bringing multidisciplinary expertise to the field of spatial planning, both as a practical endeavour and an academic discipline. Moreover, it has provided insights into sociology and social and urban studies, which align closely with the objectives of the platial agenda. The success achieved thus far in this experience can be directly attributed to the dedicated and engaged efforts of our students.

Notes

1. More about the project structure can be found on <https://raumplanung.tu-dortmund.de/studium/bachelor-raumplanung/projektstudium/projekte/>
2. The Place Standard Tool is of public access through <https://www.ourplace.scot/tool>
3. More about the Place Standard partners on <https://www.ourplace.scot/about-us>
4. <https://www.pharos.nl/kennisbank/de-leefplekometer-wat-vind-je-van-je-leefplek/>

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